

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Name of Complex.	Appearance and Colour.	Proposed formula.	Percentage of element.									
			Cr.		N		C		H.		O	
			Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.
Quinoline.	Dark brown	$R_2Cr(CrO_{10})$	19.94	20.01	5.34	5.32	43.29	41.37	2.67	2.70	28.76	30.60
8-Hydroxy quinoline.	powder Green powder	$R_2Cr(CrO_{10})$	18.77	19.02	5.04	5.08	38.99	40.10	2.52	2.54	34.68	33.26

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MEASUREMENT OF THE COMPLEXES.

Current passed 4.5 amp ; Temperature = 27° ; $K_{air} = 0.028 \times 10^{-6}$; $K_{water} = -0.720 \times 10^{-6}$

Sl. No.	Volume susceptibility $K \times 10^{-6}$	Effective density (ρ)	Mass susceptibility $K' = K/\rho \times 10^{-6}$	Molar susceptibility $K_m \times 10^{-6}$	Number of Bohr Magnetic associated with the molecule. ($\mu\beta$)
<u>Quinoline Complex, $(C_9H_7N)CrCrO_{10}$</u>					
1.	4.650	0.4463	10.35	5409	3.618
2.	4.650	0.4463	10.35	5409	3.618
<u>8-hydroxy quinoline complex, $(C_9H_6OHN)_2CrCrO_{10}$</u>					
1.	4.503	0.4491	10.02	5551.08	3.667
2.	4.486	0.4491	9.984	5534.12	3.661

The values of Bohr Magnetons obtained in Col. 5 support the presence of Cr (III) in both the complexes.

Determination of oxidising powers of the complexes : Definite weights of the complexes were dissolved in minimum volume of *N*-NaOH solution and the solution was made upto a definite volume with distilled water. Oxidising powers of complexes were determined iodometrically as suggested by Tomar, Singh and Singh.¹¹

Estimation of Chromium in the basic part and determination of the oxidising power of the filtrate : Chromium in the basic part of the complexes was estimated (i) Volumetrically and (ii) Gravimetrically as described by Tomar, Singh and Singh (loc. cit.). Oxidising power of the filtrate (obtained from gravimetric method) was also determined by the method used by the above workers.

This study suggests that Chromium is present in equal proportions in the acidic as well as basic parts of the complexes.

Magnetic measurements : Molar magnetic susceptibility (K_m) of the complexes was determined by Gouy's method at room temperature (Table 2).

I. R. Studies : Infra-red spectrograms of the complexes were obtained by using PERKIN-ELMER-MODEL 521 (4000 cm^{-1} to 250 cm^{-1})

Discussion

The observations made with the chemical and analytical studies of the complexes along with their behaviour in magnetic field and I.R. examination clearly show that (i) Both the complexes contain chromium in acidic and basic parts and the amount of the chromium in both the parts is equal (ii) The base molecule is attached to the blue perchromate molecule in both complexes (iii) On the basis of analytical data the probable molecular formula for both the complexes can be written as $R_2Cr(CrO_{10})$ where R stands for base molecule.

On examining the possibility of attachment of the base molecule in the two probable formulae for blue perchromate i.e. CrO_8 and $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_9$, it seems quite probable in the latter formula as it has the necessary Cr(III) for complex formation. The study of these complexes, therefore, favours $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_8$ formula for blue perchromate.

References

- O. F. WIEDE., *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 3139.
- K. A. HOFMANN and H. HIENDLMAIER., *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3059., and 1906, 39, 3181.
- E. H. RISENFELD., *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 3941.
- R. SCHWARZ and H. GIESE., *Ber.*, 1932, 65B, 871..
- R. C. RAI., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 68 ; 1965, 42, 387 and 1967, 45, 492.
- C. V. PILLAI and R. C. RAI. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 634
- B. S. RAJPUL, P. K. GOVIL and N. K. SINGHAL., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 311,
- B. T. TJIABES., *Proc. Acad. Sc. Amsterdam.*, 1933, 35, 639.
- W. KLEMM and J. WERTH., *Z. anorg. allgem Chem.* 1933, 216, 127.
- S. BHATNAGAR, B. PRAKASH and A. HAMID., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1428.
- O. P. TOMAR, R. SINGH and J. SINGH., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 209.

Effect of Ring Size and 2-Methyl Substituents on the Rate of Elimination of Cycloalkyltosylates in Dimethyl Sulfoxide

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ELMINATION reactions of alcohols,¹ alkylhalides² and alkyl tosylates^{2,3,4} in dimethyl sulfoxide has been studied previously.⁵ While some effort has been expended to reveal the mechanism by which the

elimination of some alkyl tosylates takes place, no effort has been made to study the substituent effect in the elimination of medium sized ring alkyl tosylates in dimethyl sulfoxide. In a previous paper⁶ it was proposed that the elimination takes place through an ion-pair rather than through a carbonium ion for which some evidence was cited. In this study the rates of 2-methyl-cycloalkyl tosylates are compared with the parent compounds to find the effect of 2-methyl substituent on the rate of elimination especially the cyclopentyl and cycloheptyl systems. It is hoped that the information obtained will shed some light on the steric effects and conformation for these systems. Table (1) shows the rate data for the elimination reaction of parent cycloalkyl tosylate systems while Table 2 shows rate constants for the elimination reaction of 2-methyl-cycloalkyl tosylates.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR ELIMINATION OF CYCLOALKYL TOSYLATES IN DMSO AT 50.0°

Alkyl Tosylate	K_1 , mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Relative rate to Cyclohexyl
Cyclopentyl	5.9×10^{-6}	16.25
Cyclohexyl	3.6×10^{-7}	1
Cycloheptyl	4.6×10^{-6}	12.6
Cyclooctyl	5.5×10^{-5}	152

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE ELIMINATION OF 2-METHYL CYCLOALKYL TOSYLATES IN DMSO AT 50.0°.

Alkyl Tosylate	K_1 , mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Relative rate to parent compound
<i>trans</i> -2-Methylcyclopentyl	2.4×10^{-5}	4.1
<i>trans</i> -2-Methylcyclohexyl	8.9×10^{-7}	2.5
<i>cis</i> -2-Methylcyclohexyl	3.5×10^{-5}	97.0
<i>trans</i> -2-Methylcycloheptyl	7.25×10^{-5}	15.8
<i>trans</i> -2-Methylcyclooctyl	2.1×10^{-4}	3.8

Discussion

From the rate study of the elimination reaction of cycloalkyl tosylates in DMSO, it appears that the rate of cyclooctyl system is the fastest of all cycloalkyl tosylates studied, and is faster than the cyclohexyl by a factor of 152. This is not unexpected since the strain in the cyclooctyl is the largest and in the cyclohexyl is least, while the cyclopentyl and cycloheptyl systems showed almost rates.

In a similar study by Brown⁷ for the acetolysis of tosylates the observed rates at 25° exhibit a change in relative rate from a low of 1.00 for cyclohexyl to a high of 583 for the cyclooctyl. This supports the idea that a carbonium ion intermediate might not be formed in the elimination of tosylates in DMSO. By comparing the rate data for the parent cycloalkyl compounds with those for 2-Methylcycloalkyl tosylates it could be shown that in general terms the rate has increased from a minimum of 2.5 for *trans*-2-methylcyclohexyl to a maximum of 15.8 for *trans*-2-methyl cycloheptyl with the exception of 97 for the *cis*-2-methylcyclohexyl which is expected to be so since the tosylate leaving group in (I) can adopt an anti-periplanar conformation while in (II) it cannot.

Solvolysis of 3-substituted cyclopentyls were previously studied using different substituents and the effect on the rate of solvolysis was found negligible⁸.

The unexpected low results for the relative rate in the elimination of *trans*-2-methylcyclooctyl to the parent cyclooctyl tosylate might indicate that larger substituents like a methyl group might take up preferred conformation with normal bond angles and better staggered arrangements. It should be pointed out that the elimination in DMSO is quite facile at this temperature and could be used for synthetic purposes.

Experimental

Preparation of Tosylates: All alkyl tosylates were prepared from purified dried and distilled alcohols. 0.1 mole of each alcohol was dissolved in 80 ml. of spectro quality pyridine and cooled to -10°. Recrystallized *p*-toluene sulfonyl chloride (19.1 g, 0.1 mole) dissolved in 20 ml. pyridine was added to the cold mixture with strong stirring for three hours. The temperature of the mixture was not allowed to get higher than 0°. The mixture was left in the refrigerator overnight. The mixture was then poured into a solution of 5*N* sulfuric acid and the tosylate extracted with ether, washed twice with cold acid and then with dilute cadmium chloride. After drying the solution over magnesium sulfate, the solvent was evaporated and the tosylate crystallized, if it is a solid, until a constant melting point or letting it under 0.1 mm. vacuum for few hours.

Rate Study

A thermostatic oil bath at 50° ± 0.1 was used to conduct the study. 0.02*M* solution of the tosylate was prepared and equilibrated. Two ml of that solution was introduced in 10 ml ampoules and were placed in the bath. Samples were analysed for the liberated sulfonic acid at different periods of time. Standardized sodium hydroxide was used to determine the sulfonic acid and phenolphthalin was the indicator.

References

1. J. V. TRAYNELIV, L. W. HERGENROTHER, R. J. LIVINGSTON, and A. J. VALICENT., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27 2377.
2. H. R. NACE, *Chemistry and Industry* (London) 1958, 1629.
3. D. N. JONES and M. A. SAEED., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4657.
4. F. JAIREAU, M. B. TCHOUBAR and R. GOUTARELL., *Bull. Chim. Soc. France*, 1962, 887.
5. For a review of DMSO technical data and references see "Technical information on Dimethyl Sulfoxide" by Crown Zellerbach Corp. 1962.
6. L. F. HATCH, S. M. MATAR, A. GAWISH., *Indian J. Chem.*, (In press).
7. H. C. BROWN and G. J. HAM., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2735.
8. I. LILLIEN and K. KHALELUDDIN., *Chemistry and Industry*, 1964, 1028.